

a heterocyclic ring, such as oxadiazole and *s*-triazole led to the compounds possessing various biological activities².

Prompted by these observations and in continuation of our studies on condensed heterocycles^{3,4}, we undertook preparation of a series of diaryloxymethyl-substituted-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (3a-o) and screen their antibacterial activity.

2,5-Diaryloxymethyl-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (3a-o) were obtained by the condensation of 3-aryloxymethyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles (1)⁴ with substituted aryloxyacetic acids (2) using phosphorus oxychloride as cyclising agent (Scheme 1). Compounds 2 were prepared from substituted phenols and monochloroacetic acid⁵.

Scheme 1

Synthesis of some 2,5-Diaryloxymethyl-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles†

B. SHIVARAMA HOLLA, ALPHONSUS D'SOUZA**
and

BALAKRISHNA KALLURAYA*

Department of Post-Graduate Studies and Research in
Chemistry, Mangalore University,
Mangalagangothri-574 199

Manuscript received 19 December 1990, accepted 8 April 1991

1,3,4-Thiadiazoles are found to be associated with diverse biological, industrial and analytical uses¹. Incorporation of an aryloxyalkyl substituent into

† Presented at the 8th Annual Conference of Indian Council of Chemists, held at Tirupati, 1988.

** Present address: Department of Chemistry, St. Philomena's College, Mysore-570 015.

Compounds (3a-o) were characterised by elemental analysis, ir, ¹H nmr and mass spectral data (Table 1). In the ir spectra NH absorptions around 3 100-3 300 cm⁻¹ characteristic of the triazoles (1) disappeared in case of the triazolothiadiazoles (3), thereby confirming the assigned structure⁵. The nmr spectrum of 3a is in conformity with the assigned structure. The two OCH₂ protons resonated as singlets at δ 5.20 and 5.35. The signals of the aromatic protons of the two *p*-chlorophenyl⁶ rings overlapped with each other and appeared as a multiplet at δ 6.7-7.2, integrating for eight protons. Further evidence for the triazolothiadiazole structure was obtained from mass spectrum of 3i: *m/z* 438, consistent with the molecular formula C₂₅H₁₈N₄O₂S.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE THIADIAZOLES (3a-o)*

Compd. no.	Ar	Ar'	M.p.** °C	Yield %	Colour and crystal form
3a	4-Chlorophenyl	4-Chlorophenyl	110	65	White flakes
3b	4-Chlorophenyl	2,4-Dimethylphenyl	98	61	White needles
3c	1-Naphthyl	4-Chlorophenyl	185	60	White needles
3d	1-Naphthyl	4-Methylphenyl	145	65	Brown flakes
3e	1-Naphthyl	3,5-Dimethylphenyl	80	63	Brown needles
3f	1-Naphthyl	2-Naphthyl	122	59	Yellow needles
3g	2-Naphthyl	2-Chlorophenyl	115	65	Yellow flakes
3h	2-Naphthyl	4-Methylphenyl	118	60	White needles
3i	2-Naphthyl	2-Naphthyl	123	59	White flakes
3j	2-Chlorophenyl	2-Naphthyl	112	66	Brown flakes
3k	2-Chlorophenyl	4-Methylphenyl	105	53	Brown needles
3l	2-Chlorophenyl	3,5-Dimethylphenyl	131	57	Brown needles
3m	4-Methylphenyl	3,5-Dimethylphenyl	89	62	Pale brown needles
3n	4-Chlorophenyl	3,5-Dimethylphenyl	128-29	66	Brown needles
3o	2-Methylphenyl	3,5-Dimethylphenyl	106-07	63	Brown flakes

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis. **Solvent of crystallisation : Ethyl alcohol.

The molecular ion further underwent loss of a naphthyloxy radical to give an ion at $m/z=295$, which is a characteristic property of aryloxymethyl substituted heterocycles⁷.

Antibacterial activity : Compounds 3a-o were tested for their antibacterial activity *in vitro* against *B. subtilis* and *A. aerogenes* employing the disc-diffusion method⁸ and only 3d, 3j and 3m showed significant activity against both the microorganisms.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, nmr spectrum on a Varian (60 MHz) spectrometer and mass spectrum on a Jeol-JMS-D300 spectrometer operating at 70 eV.

2,5-Diaryloxymethyl-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (3a-o). *General procedure :* A mixture of 1 (0.02 mol) and aryloxyacetic acid (2 ; 0.02 mol) in phosphorus oxychloride (10 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The excess phosphorus oxychloride was then removed under reduced pressure. The mixture was cooled and poured into ice-cold water and the resulting solid was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate followed by water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Head, R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for analytical and mass spectral data.

References

1. L. L. BAMBAS in "Comprehensive Heterocyclic Chemistry", eds. A. R. KATRITZKY and C. W. REES, Pergamon, Oxford, 1952, Vol. 4, p. 81 ; Lubrizol Corp., US Pat. 4 246 126/1981 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1981, 94, 1425054).
2. T. RAMALINGAM, A. A. DESHMUKH, P. B. SATTUR, V. K. SHETH and S. R. NAIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 269.
3. B. S. HOLLA, B. KALLURAYA and K. R. SRIDHAR, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1988, 33, 277.
4. B. S. HOLLA and B. KALLURAYA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, 27, 683.
5. "Vogel's Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", eds. B. S. FURNIS, A. J. HANNAFORD, V. ROGERS, P. W. G. SMITH and A. R. TATCHELL, ELBS, London, 1984, p. 754.
6. "The Aldrich Library of NMR Spectra", Aldrich Chemical Co., Wisconsin, 1974, 6, 21.
7. B. S. HOLLA, B. KALLURAYA and S. C. NATH, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1988, 330, 549.
8. R. GRUICKSHANK, J. P. DUGUID, B. P. MORNION and R. H. A. SWAIN, "Medicinal Microbiology", Churchill-Livingstone, New York, 1975, Vol. II, p. 190.